

THE PLACE OF MAKEUP AND COSTUMES IN PUBLIC CELEBRATIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the importance of makeup and costumes in folk festivals, the preservation of cultural heritage and the strengthening of solidarity in society through them. Costumes and makeup worn on national holidays are symbols that represent the historical past, traditions and cultural characteristics of the people. The article also examines the impact of state policy and cultural initiatives on festive clothes and makeup, their role in society and their contribution to the development of culture.

Keywords: Folk festivals, makeup, costumes, national identity, cultural values, cultural development, historical traditions, festive clothes, social context, cultural heritage, unity in society.

INTRODUCTION

Folk festivals and cultural events around the world play a key role in demonstrating the cultural heritage, historical traditions, social and aesthetic values of peoples and nations. Every nation and culture is distinguished by its festive costumes and makeup, because these clothes are not only important elements of appearance, but also reflect the spiritual state of the people, the purpose and content of the holiday. In countries with a rich cultural heritage like Uzbekistan, the costumes worn and makeup used during folk holidays play a major role in strengthening national identity and unifying society.¹

Holidays are an important opportunity not only to create a spiritual festive mood, but also to preserve national values, respect history and strengthen social cohesion. At such events, national clothes are used as symbols reflecting the cultural characteristics and ethnic traditions of each nation. Makeup, in addition to making the holiday more attractive and beautiful, is also an important tool for expressing relationships between people. Festive costumes and makeup play a key role in highlighting the social and cultural situation, as well as ensuring unity in society and developing national values.

¹ T.M.Rashidov (2022). KONSERT IJODKORLIGI: TUR, JANR VA SHAKLLAR. Oriental Art and Culture, 3 (4), 79-91.

Mass holidays and cultural events are an integral part of social life, and each nation and people express their traditions, historical and cultural values through these holidays. Holidays in the Republic of Uzbekistan play an important role not only in ensuring national unity and harmony, but also in preserving and developing the cultural and ethnic identity of the people. Makeup and clothes used during the holidays, in turn, are important as tools reflecting social, cultural and historical characteristics.

Makeup and costumes used during holidays play an important role in preserving national values and passing them on to new generations. They are important not only for appearance, but also for expressing national identity. At the same time, the reforms and legal documents carried out in the field of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including presidential decrees and resolutions, emphasize the role and social significance of festive makeup and costumes.

Also, the cultural heritage, ethnic and historical identity of Uzbekistan are reflected in festive costumes. Each holiday has its own costumes and makeup, which are of great importance in renewing national values and traditions, strengthening the unity of society. Documents adopted by the President of Uzbekistan, including the decrees and resolutions "On the Development of Culture", determine the importance of festive makeup and costumes in the development of national traditions and the preservation of culture.²

OBJECTIVES AND METHODS OF THE RESEARCH

Make-up and costumes at public holidays and cultural events play an important role not only in decorating the appearance, but also in reflecting the cultural values, national identity and historical traditions of the people.

The main goal of the study is to analyze the cultural, social and historical significance of make-up and costumes at public holidays. The study plans to analyze the role of festive costumes and make-up in society, their social and cultural significance among peoples, as well as the provisions of the laws and decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan that pay special attention to them.³

The methods used in the study include literature analysis, document study, practical observations and social surveys. The study collected information on the cultural and social significance of festive costumes and makeup based on the decrees, laws, resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and international conventions. The results of the study help to better understand the cultural role and social significance of makeup and costumes during national holidays.

² B. Sayfullayev, J. Mamatqosimov. Aktyorlik mahorati. — T., Fan va texnologiya, 2012.

³ I. Jabbarov. O'zbek xalqi etnografiyasi. — T., O'qituvchi, 2024.

RESULTS

In general, makeup and costumes play an important role in public holidays and cultural events as a means of reflecting the cultural values of society and uniting society.

If we look at the history of makeup art, the first signs of makeup tools can be seen in sources related to the history of ancient Egypt, when makeup served as a sign of wealth that pleased the gods. The creation of delicate eyelids with paints, characteristic of Egyptian art, appeared in men and women around 4000 BC. In Greek and Roman theater, the use of masks by actors eliminated the need for makeup, so they used only masks rather than make-up or make-up. There is also an ancient account of the invention of the mask by Thespis (a Greek poet, 6th century BC), as well as a story that the mask replaced makeup.⁴

1-Table

CLASSIFICATION OF MAKEUP AND COSTUMES⁵

Categories	Grim	Clothes
Appearance	- Light (makeup intended for the face)	- National costumes (Navruz, Independence Day, etc.)
	- Light-colored (symbol of the awakening of nature and life)	- Wedding costumes (used for large events)
Purpose	- Colors such as black, red, gold (colors representing the heart, love, strength)	- Formal and informal costumes (worn at holidays or social events)
	- Correcting and making the appearance more beautiful	- Representing cultural traditions and preserving historical values
Method	- Showing symbolic meaning (for example, at weddings, birthdays)	- Strengthening national identity and unifying society

⁴ Tara Maginnis. History of Theatre Makeup before 1920. 2008

⁵ Mamasoliyeva Muxtasar To'xtasin Qizi (2024). GRIM SAN'ATI. Science and innovation, 3 (Special Issue 36), 368-370. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11214648

Appearance	- Applying makeup to the face (permitted colors and methods)	- Flattering, embellished costumes (especially for holidays)
	- Mascara, lipstick, eyebrow pencil, etc.	- Wedding and festive costumes: custom designer costumes, national costumes
Cultural and social context	- Grimms reflect the traditional values of the people during national holidays and cultural events	- Festive clothes strengthen the social unity of the people
Symbolic significance	- Demonstration of the spiritual state and cultural values of the people through grimms	- Clothes worn on national holidays represent historical and cultural heritage
Depending on time and place	- Different types of grimms are used during various holidays and cultural events	- Special clothes for national holidays, special social events, weddings

1. Makeup - this includes various methods of decorating the face. During holidays, for example, on national holidays such as Navruz or Independence Day, makeup is used not only for appearance, but also reflects the state of mind of the people, important social values \u200b\u200bin the celebration of the holiday.⁶

2. Clothing - national and traditional clothing worn during holidays helps to preserve the historical past and culture of the people. There are specific costumes for each holiday, which play a major role in strengthening social unity, national identity and values.

⁶ Иванов О.К., Кривицкий К.Э. Вахтангов и Вахтанговцы. — М., 2019.

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The clothes and makeup used during holidays, including Navruz, Independence Day and other national holidays, play an important role in expressing the historical heritage of the people, their ethnic characteristics, as well as harmony between peoples. The clothes and makeup used during holidays are of great importance in creating the unique spirit of each holiday, reflecting the spiritual state of people and preserving cultural heritage.

2-Table:

Costumes and makeup used for holidays⁷

Holiday/Event	Clothing	Grimms	Significance
Navruz	National clothing, folk costumes	Neighborhood grimms, representing nature	Expression of national values, respect for nature
Independence Day	Formal clothing, national forms	Light grimms, colorful	Celebration of Uzbekistan's independence, strengthening the national spirit
New Year	New Year's themed clothing	New Year's character grimms	Anticipation of the New Year, strengthening unity in society

DISCUSSIONS

Holiday costumes and make-up are an important means of preserving national traditions, ethnic identities and historical memories. They are not only external elements visible during holidays, but they also play an important role in strengthening social relations in society, ensuring harmony between peoples. Another difficult aspect of organizing public holidays is that they can be rehearsed only once or twice, at most three times.⁸

The role of makeup and costumes in public holidays and cultural events is not only to express appearance, but also to reflect important meanings and values in social life. Costumes and makeup used during national holidays of Uzbekistan, such as Navruz, Independence Day and other holidays, are distinguished not only by their external decorations, but also reflect national values, historical traditions and the unity of the people. It is necessary to analyze from a scientific point of view the national costumes and makeup used during the holidays, their aesthetic and spiritual

⁷ Encyclopedia Britannica. Volume IV, Retrieved 2021-06-29

⁸ F.Ahmedov. Ommaviy tadbir va bayramlar rejissurasi va aktyorlik mahorati. — T., 2007

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significance and their role in society. Festive costumes and makeup play a major role in the formation of national identity and the unification of the people. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the clothes used during holidays are an integral part of the preservation and development of the cultural heritage of the people. Through such costumes, society shows respect for its historical past and helps to convey national values to future generations. The use of national costumes during holidays helps to call people to unity and increase respect for their culture and traditions.

Makeup also plays an important role in the festive atmosphere. Makeup used during holidays is purposefully aimed at making the appearance more beautiful, and sometimes symbolically meaningful. For example, during some holidays, especially Navruz, makeup not only shows the aesthetic side of the appearance, but can also reflect themes such as the awakening of nature, the renewal of life, the arrival of spring and warmth. This makeup is not only an external appearance, but also a means of expressing the spirit of the holiday, the values of the people and a positive attitude to life.

It is also necessary to take into account the social and cultural context when analyzing festive costumes and makeup. The importance of clothes and makeup during national holidays is not only in aesthetic or decorative elements, but also in the fact that they reflect changes and social trends taking place in society. All initiatives aimed at developing the culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and preserving national values, including the restoration of the importance of national costumes and make-up. The costumes used during holidays and cultural events strengthen the unity of society by demonstrating the historical monuments, traditions and national pride of the people.

The importance of make-up and costumes during cultural events and holidays, as well as their influence, affect not only the appearance, but also the inner world of the people. There is a need to study their symbolic and aesthetic significance, their huge role in preserving and developing the culture of the people.

Make-up and costumes in society reflect not only appearance, but also national identity, preservation of cultural heritage, ensuring social harmony and respect for cultural differences. Make-up and costumes used during holidays are an important means of preserving national traditions and values, and through them, passing them on to the future.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The role and significance of makeup and costumes during public holidays play a major role in the cultural life of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the preservation and development of national values. They serve not only to decorate holidays, but also to express the historical and cultural identity of the people. Presidential decrees and resolutions emphasize the important role of festive costumes and makeup in preserving national traditions and developing culture. Festive costumes

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and makeup serve as an important tool in ensuring social and cultural stability in society and strengthening national unity.

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